

GUIDELINES FOR THE DIGITALIZATION OF ECOSERVICES PROVIDED BY CERTIFIED FORESTS

Digital tools and technology systems for the sustainable
management of Mediterranean forest resources

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1. Introduction

The Mediterranean region boasts over 25 million hectares of forests and approximately 50 million hectares of other wooded lands. Changes in climate and socio-economic conditions in the Mediterranean region pose significant threats to forests, potentially leading to the loss of ecosystem services and triggering a wide array of economic, social, and environmental challenges. The forest-wood supply chain in European Mediterranean (EUMED) countries currently faces low competitiveness, exacerbated by the limited access of forest managers and companies to up-to-date digital technologies. Some of these technologies are outdated or fail to address crucial industry challenges anticipated in the coming decades. This situation underscores the need for an urgent multi-actor approach to digitalization, starting with an understanding of stakeholders' needs and collaborative actions. DigiMedFor's overarching goal is to revolutionize the technological landscape of the Mediterranean forest-wood supply chain, enhancing its competitiveness and enabling stakeholders to effectively manage and provide various forest ecosystem services (FES), including wood traceability from forests to end-users. Aligned with the EU forest and digital strategies, DigiMedFor will leverage advanced digital solutions to enhance the monitoring and management of forest resources along the supply chain, optimizing wood production sustainability, traceability, and ESS delivery. The project will integrate geo-spatial, AI, and modelling technologies synergistically with ICT to achieve its objectives (DigiMedFor Project, 2023).

The Mediterranean region, with forested areas and wooded lands, faces significant challenges due to climate and socio-economic changes. These challenges could lead to the loss of vital ESS and trigger economic, social, and environmental issues. In EUMED countries, the low competitiveness of the forest-wood supply chain is further compounded by limited access to digital technologies. Outdated systems and unaddressed industry challenges are hurdles that must be overcome urgently. DigiMedFor recognizes the importance of a multi-actor approach to digitalization, beginning with understanding stakeholders' needs and defining collaborative actions to address them. Together, DigiMedFor aims to create a greener future, ensuring the thriving of forests and the safeguarding of ESS (DigiMedFor Project, 2023).

Ecosystem Services (ESS) are described by the European Union as the benefits humans receive from ecosystems that sustain life and promote economic and social well-being (European Union, n.d.). These services are generally classified into four groups: provisioning services, such as food, freshwater, and raw materials; regulating services, including climate regulation and water purification; cultural services, encompassing recreational, aesthetic, and spiritual benefits; and supporting services, like nutrient cycling and soil formation, which are fundamental to the provision of the other services (European Union, n.d.; Haines-Young & Potschin, 2012).

The importance of ESS lies in their foundational role in maintaining environmental balance and directly influencing public health, climate resilience, and economic productivity. For example, ecosystems rich in biodiversity help regulate floods, store carbon, and pollinate crops—functions essential to climate adaptation and food security. The European Environment Agency stresses that the ongoing loss of biodiversity and degradation of natural systems threaten these vital services, highlighting the urgency of ecosystem restoration and sustainable land use (EEA, 2023; EEA, 2024). Additionally, the significance of ecosystem services was highlighted in the INCA project report by Vysna et al. (2021), which estimated that ESS in the EU provided an economic value of around EUR 234 billion in 2019—an amount comparable to the combined gross value added by agriculture and forestry. Given this importance, in the DigiMedFor scope, the Task 3.4 aims to highlight the value of ESS and demonstrate how certified forests contribute to these ESS.

1.1. Objectives of the Guideline

The guidelines for the digitization of ESS provided by certified forests aim to expand the range of information accessible through the system developed by PEFC Spain. The main objective is to facilitate communication with all forest areas that comply with the PEFC Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) System in Catalonia, Spain, as well as with forest owners, managers, and end-users who benefit from forest ESS. This involves establishing a systematic link between each forest management unit (FMU) and the corresponding Ecosystem and Cultural Services indicators.

Objectives:

- **Enhanced information accessibility:** The guideline aims to improve the availability and transparency of information related to the ESS provided by PEFC-certified forests. By digitizing this ESS, forest owners/ managers, stakeholders and end-users will have access to a comprehensive overview of the ESS offered by these forests.
- **Promoting SFM:** By integrating ESS indicators, the guideline actively supports and promote the principles of SFM endorsed by the PEFC Spain. By highlighting the multifunctional roles of forests, also the guideline encourages practices that balance environmental, social, and economic considerations.
- **Fostering stakeholder engagement:** By increasing the accessibility of information on the PEFC Spain platform, the guideline aims to involve a broader range of stakeholders. This inclusive approach fosters transparency, accountability, and collaboration among forest managers, certification bodies, policymakers, researchers, and the public.
- **Enabling replication and scalability:** The guideline is designed to be adaptable across different geographical and institutional contexts, enabling their replication in other countries. This objective supports the broader application of the framework to a variety of forest certification systems and management settings beyond Spain, contributing to global efforts in SFM and ESS communication.

The analysis and evaluation of ESS focused on PEFC-certified FMU areas within Catalonia region, Spain, as shown in Figure 1, and the detailed spatial distribution of ESS data in relation to the PEFC-certified FMUs is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Location of Task 3.4: ESS data from Forestry Laboratory and PEFC-certified areas in the Catalonia region. Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 2. Details of the ESS information overlapped with the PEFC-certified FMUs. Source: own elaboration.

By outlining clear objectives, this guideline serves as a foundational framework for advancing the digitization of ESS in certified forests, thereby promoting SFM practices and providing forest owners, managers, and end-users with increased awareness of the ESS their forests provide, along with access to a digital tool to support communication and decision-making.

1.2. Guideline Roadmap

This guideline is structured into three main sections:

- **Digitalization of ESS within the PEFC Platform:** Integration of ESS data into certification systems to support SFM, which has been highlighted as a main objective.
- **Guidelines for ESS Digitalization: A Case Study of Forestry Laboratory:** This demonstrates the establishment of a Forestry Laboratory in the Replication sites in order to facilitate ESS digitalization and monitoring.

- [Guidelines for Developing a PEFC National Forest Certification System](#): Step-by-step instructions for adapting and implementing forest certification in new contexts.

1.3. Relevance for Targeted Stakeholders

The guideline for the “Digitalization of Ecoservices Provided by Certified Forests” is developed to support a broad and diverse group of stakeholders whose activities, responsibilities, or interests are connected to forest ecosystems and SFM. By linking ecosystem and cultural services to FMUs through a digital framework, the guideline enhances stakeholder engagement, transparency, and informed decision-making across various levels—from local forest owners to certification bodies and international partners. This digital integration has the potential to transform forest governance by fostering collaboration, improving resource allocation, and accelerating the adoption of sustainable practices.

- **Forest Owners and Managers**

Forest owners and managers are the primary actors in the implementation of SFM practices. The digitalization of ESS enables them to better understand, document, and communicate the ecological and cultural values their forests provide. It supports decision-making through accessible, indicator-based data that links their FMUs with ESS. This empowers Forest owners and managers to demonstrate compliance with sustainability standards and enhances the value proposition of forest certification. As a result, forest owners can expect improved management efficiency, stronger market positioning for certified products, and increased opportunities for income diversification through ESS payments or incentives.

- **Policy Makers and Public Authorities**

The inclusion of digitized ESS indicators enables valuable insights for policy makers and governmental organizations responsible for forest planning, biodiversity protection, and climate adaptation, and other related areas. The systematic documentation and visualization of ESS contribute to more informed policy development and enhance the capacity of authorities to support evidence-based planning and funding allocation. Ultimately, this

guideline can drive more effective and adaptive policy frameworks that better safeguard forest ecosystems while optimizing public investments and regulatory outcomes.

- **Researchers and Technical Experts**

For the scientific and technical stakeholders, the guideline presents a standardized methodology for monitoring, evaluating, and visualizing ESS. It opens new opportunities for interdisciplinary research, particularly in fields such as remote sensing, environmental modeling, and sustainability assessment. With this, the common framework fosters innovation by enabling comparative studies, improving data quality of ESS, and accelerating the development of new innovative tools and methodologies for scientific and technical stakeholders.

- **End Users and the Public**

End users—including local communities, forest visitors, and the general public—benefit from increased awareness and understanding of the multifunctional roles that forests play. The digital platform supported by this guideline can help bridge the knowledge gap between forest management practices and the benefits people receive from forests, thereby fostering stronger support for sustainable forest policies and certification schemes which increase responsible behavior toward forest conservation.

- **International and Replication Partners**

Finally, for organizations and countries interested in adopting or replicating this framework, the guideline offers a scalable and adaptable model structured around three key components. It facilitates the effective transfer of knowledge, digital tools, and methodologies across borders, supporting the advancement of SFM and the communication of ESS in diverse ecological, institutional, and cultural contexts. Importantly, this framework also serves as a strategic reference point for non-EU countries seeking to align with sustainable forest certification and monitoring practices, helping them adopt innovative, digitally supported approaches to forest stewardship.

2. Ecosystem Services (ESS)

Forests around the world play a crucial role in providing a wide range of ESS essential for human well-being (Brockerhoff et al., 2017) and environmental sustainability (MEA, 2005). These services, including water provision, climate regulation, and recreational opportunities, are integral to support biodiversity and maintain the balance of ecosystems (IPBES, 2019; MEA, 2005). However, Mediterranean forests face significant threats from human activities and changing climatic conditions, leading to deforestation, fragmentation, and loss of biodiversity (FAO, 2020). Despite efforts outlined in initiatives such as the UN 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the EU 2020 Biodiversity Strategy, challenges persist in accurately assessing and quantifying these ESS (UN 2015; European Commission, 2011). Tools like forest function mapping (FFM) are employed to integrate various forest functions and support management decisions, yet gaps remain in quantifying public demand and comprehensively assessing the ESS. To address these limitations, there is a growing emphasis on supplementing FFM with the ecosystem service approach, which proposes indicators to quantify FESs biophysically and align frameworks for better comparability and management. Through such integrated approaches, it is hoped that the importance of forests and their ESS in Europe will be better understood and effectively managed for future generations (Nocentini et al., 2022; Morán-Ordóñez et al., 2020; Anaya-Romero et al., 2016; Noce & Santini, 2018).

According to the study by Berghöfer and Schneider (2015), the concept of ESS offers a way to bridge the gap between development and conservation by recognizing the numerous benefits of nature that provides to society. This perspective highlights that maintaining healthy ecosystems is crucial for resilient development worldwide. ESS plays a vital role in our economy, culture, health, and well-being (MEA, 2005; TEEB, 2009). To understand the connections between specific actions, their environmental impacts, and subsequent societal consequences, an 'ESS lens' is essential (Berghöfer & Schneider, 2015). This lens considers both the supply and demand sides, emphasizing the importance of their relationship in policy and public management. ESS indicators are instrumental in adopting this perspective, providing comprehensive information about conditions, trends, and pressures related to nature's benefits. These ESS indicators often combine measurements of the supply and

use/demand of ecosystem benefits. However, finding suitable indicators tailored to specific information needs can be challenging (Berghöfer & Schneider, 2015). Guidance from organizations such as the UNEP World Conservation Monitoring Centre and methodologies presented by Brown et al. (2014) support the effective development and use of ESS indicators. These ESS indicators should be relevant to the context, scientifically sound, transparent, and feasible to implement (Fisher et al., 2009). The selection of indicators must be purpose-driven and tailored to the target audience, as different objectives—such as policymaking, planning, awareness-raising, or accountability—demand different kinds of data (Brown et al., 2014) emphasize that clearly identifying information needs is a critical first step in designing such indicators. Selecting an appropriate combination of indicators then involves assessing data availability, practicality, and the trade-offs between additional monitoring costs and the added value of more precise information.

2.1. Classification of ESS

The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES), developed by Haines-Young and Potschin (2012) in version 4.3, provides a structured approach for categorizing ecosystem services. It was designed to support the valuation, mapping, and integration of these services into environmental accounting systems. The latest version, CICES 5.2, published by Haines-Young in 2023, introduces refinements such as clearer distinctions between cultivated and wild resources under provisioning services, and improvements in the cultural services typology to enhance mapping and valuation efforts.

CICES organizes ESS into distinct categories and subcategories to enable detailed classification. The main structure is outlined as follows:

I. Provisioning services

These services are the products obtained from ecosystems. They include:

- Food: Products derived from plants, animals and microbes for consumption.
- Water: Freshwater provided for drinking, irrigation and industrial use.
- Raw materials: Resources such as wood, fibre and fuel.

- Genetic resources: Genes and genetic information used for crop improvement and biotechnology.
- Medicinal resources: Plants and animals used for pharmaceuticals and traditional medicines (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2012).

II. Regulating and maintenance services

These services are the benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes.

- Air quality regulation: The role of ecosystems in cleaning and maintaining air quality.
- Climate regulation: Influence of ecosystems on climate, including carbon sequestration.
- Water regulation: Regulation of water flow, storage and flood control.
- Erosion control: Prevention of soil erosion through vegetation cover.
- Pest and disease control: Natural pest and disease control through predators and biotic interactions.
- Pollination: Pollination of crops and wild plants.
- Waste treatment: Natural decomposition and assimilation of waste materials (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2012).

III. Cultural services

These services are the non-material benefits that people derive from ecosystems through spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, reflection, leisure and aesthetic experiences.

- Recreation and tourism: Opportunities for recreational activities and tourism.
- Aesthetic value: Beauty and inspiration derived from ecosystems.
- Spiritual and religious value: Spiritual and religious significance of ecosystems.
- Cognitive development: Opportunities for education and learning provided by ecosystems (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2012).

2.2. Existing ESS in Catalonia

ESS in Catalonia, Spain, plays a vital role in sustaining the region's environment and well-being (Brotons et al., 2020). Catalonia's diverse landscapes, including agricultural areas, wetlands, and forests, offer a range of ESS. The region's natural ecosystems regulate the climate by sequestering carbon and help mitigate floods, as highlighted by Belenguer-Manzanedo et al. (2021). Catalonia's rich biodiversity, supported by the Pyrenees mountains and the Ebro Delta, is central to conservation efforts (Rodríguez-Labajos et al., 2015). Additionally, the scenic beauty of the region, from its coastlines to the Pyrenees, attracts tourists, supporting the local economy and enhancing the cultural and aesthetic aspects of the area (Tulla, 2019). These variety of ESS collectively underscore the critical interplay between nature and society in Catalonia, contributing to the well-being of its residents and shows the different ESS presence in the region of Catalonia. According to the available literature, ESS have been defined as follows in the Catalonia region.

- **Mushroom Production**

Mushroom production is the difference in the expected production of edible mushrooms (De Miguel et al. 2014) between the plots of NFI2 and NFI4. This indicator is based on a statistical model proposed to estimate the production of edible mushrooms in pine forests. The model considers the plot's composition (dominant tree species), its structure (basal area), and other characteristics such as slope, aspect, and altitude. All of these factors remain constant over time, except for the basal area, which varies between inventory datasets, specifically NFI2 and NFI4. Additionally, mushroom production is highly dependent on the specific weather conditions of the season; therefore, the model also accounts for climate variables – specifically, maximum, average, and minimum temperatures, as well as precipitation between August and December (Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

- **Exported Water (Blue water)**

Exported water is the difference in the annual averages of the relative amount of water exported from each plot (ratio of blue water to annual precipitation, De Cáceres et al. 2015) between the plots of NFI2 and NFI4. From the total amount of water that falls as precipitation in a forest, four main components can be distinguished: one part is absorbed and evapotranspired by vegetation; another is intercepted by tree canopies and trunks and

eventually evaporates as well; a third part flows downhill as runoff; and a final part infiltrates the soil beyond the reach of roots, eventually reaching rivers and aquifers. Therefore, total rainfall is distributed as follows: evapotranspiration + interception + runoff + infiltration. The first two components are used by vegetation (green water), while the last two make up what is called blue water, which is precisely what the exported water indicator refers to (Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

- **Carbon Sequestration (Carbon Sink Capacity of Forests)**

The carbon (C) sequestered by forested formations has been estimated from the tree biomass of trees with a diameter at breast height greater than 7.5 cm (obtained in National Forest Inventory – NFI 4). To do this, biomass equations from the National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (CIFOR-INIA), incorporated into the NFI at the beginning of its fourth cycle, have been used. These equations calculate the root and above-ground biomass (trunk, branches, and leaves) of each tree based on its species and the main parameters measured in the field: diameter and height. Once the approximate dry biomass is obtained, the carbon content is calculated based on the percentage by weight of carbon in dry matter according to species (e.g., as indicated by Montero et al., 2005). These percentages vary slightly, between 47–51%, so it can generally be said that about half the biomass weight corresponds to carbon (MITECO, n.d.; Vayreda et al., 2016; Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

- **Soil Organic Carbon (Soil Organic Carbon Stock in Forests)**

This measurement comes from an assessment of Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) reserves in forests, shrublands, and grasslands across peninsular Spain, based on field measurements from more than 900 soil profiles. SOC at a depth of 1 meter was modeled as a function of vegetation cover, mean annual temperature, total annual precipitation, elevation, and the interaction between temperature and elevation, while latitude and longitude were used to model the spatial correlation structure of the errors. The resulting statistical model was used to estimate SOC across the 8 million pixels of the Spanish Forest Map (29.3×10^6 ha). The soil profiles used for the calculations include data from 1975 to 2007, although SOC does not vary significantly unless there is a complete disturbance of the substrate (conversion to a non-forest soil type) (Doblas-Miranda et al., 2013; Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

- **Erosion Mitigation**

Erosion Mitigation is the difference in the amount of soil erosion prevented by vegetation (forest and shrub cover) between the plots of NFI2 and NFI4. Soil erosion control by forests refers to the amount of soil that is not eroded thanks to their presence. Tree canopies intercept and soften the impact of rainfall on the ground, while roots and leaf litter form a protective mesh that retains the soil. This indicator is calculated as the difference between the maximum potential erosion (what would occur if there were no forest cover) and the estimated erosion rate under a given forest cover. It is based on the RUSLE equation (Renard, Kenneth, et al., 1997; Panagos et al., 2015) using the formula:

$$\text{RUSLE} = L \times S \times K \times R \times C,$$

where:

L = slope length;

S = slope steepness;

K = soil type or geology;

R = rainfall erosivity (the potential of rainfall to cause erosion);

C = vegetation cover.

- **Fauna observation (Animal presence)**

Ornitho.cat is a web portal developed by the Institut Català d'Ornitologia (ICO) dedicated to the exchange of information on sightings made by enthusiasts of birds, mammals, amphibians, and many other animal groups, as well as orchids in Catalonia. For the indicator specifically, bird species richness has been used – specifically, the total number of forest bird species recorded in each municipality, as documented in 2014 (ICO, n.d.; Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

- **Cork Production**

Cork, predominantly harvested from oak trees, is used in Catalonia for crafting wine stoppers and flooring (Institut Català del Suro, n.d.).

- **Timber Production**

Timber production is the annual rate of timber stock per plot, calculated as the difference in stock (including forest growth) between the plots of NFI and NFI4. The exploitable wood generated by tree-dominated forest formations has been estimated from the tree biomass of trees with a diameter at breast height greater than 7.5 cm. To do this, biomass equations from the National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (CIFOR-INIA), incorporated into the NFI at the beginning of its fourth cycle, have been used. These equations calculate the above-ground biomass (trunk) of each tree based on its species and key parameters measured in the field: diameter and height (MITECO, n.d.; Laboratori Forestal Català., 2021).

- **Tourism and Recreation**

Catalonia's forests attract tourists and outdoor enthusiasts. National and natural parks, like Montseny and Aigüestortes i Estany de Sant Maurici, offers opportunities for hiking, wildlife watching, and eco-tourism, supporting the local tourism industry (Banqué et al., 2016).

- **Cultural Heritage**

Forests in Catalonia hold cultural importance, with traditional practices like herding, hunting, and foraging that are deeply rooted in the region's heritage (Banqué et al., 2016).

- **Firewood and Biomass**

Forests supply firewood and biomass, offering local residents a sustainable source of energy for heating and cooking (Banqué et al., 2016).

- **Water Purification**

Forests play a crucial role in maintaining water quality and regulating water supply, which is essential for agriculture, drinking water, and industrial use (Banqué, M., et al. 2016).

- **Riparian forest cover (within a 25m Buffer from Rivers)**

This is a non-exploitable forest, but it is of great importance for sustainability as it serves as a proxy for biodiversity. These forests typically host high species diversity and provide shelter for many others. They contribute to water quality by preventing runoff and help prevent

flooding by stabilizing the soil. Data obtained from the Land Cover Map of Catalonia (MCSC, 2022) and Forestry Laboratory (Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

- **Slope forest cover**

Forest cover on steep slopes (greater than 30%) is essential for mitigating soil erosion. The root systems of trees and vegetation help stabilize the soil, preventing it from being washed away during rainfall or heavy storms. Data obtained from the Land Cover Map of Catalonia (Pimentel et al., 1995; Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

2.2.1. Selected ESS

From the previous explanation of the listed ESS in Catalonia, some ESS has been selected for analysis, first for operational reasons, and secondly, those that are considered to have a higher potential interest for the forest owners. Those that the owners may already be more familiar with (such as wood production) have been excluded.

Thus, the selected ESS that are most suitable for offering an interesting product to the owners as follows:

1. Mushroom Production

This ESS was selected because it represents a valuable non-timber forest product that can generate additional income for forest owners, and it is feasible to monitor and quantify.

2. Exported Water (Blue water)

Chosen due to its relevance in understanding water availability and quality in forest areas, which is critical for ecosystem health and forest management decisions.

3. Carbon Sequestration

Selected because it plays a central role in climate change mitigation and offers opportunities for forest owners to benefit from carbon credit markets.

4. Soil Organic Carbon

Included as it reflects soil health and fertility, which are essential for sustaining forest productivity and resilience.

5. Erosion Mitigation

Chosen for its importance in protecting soil and water resources, reducing risks of land degradation that affect forest sustainability.

6. Fauna Observation (Animal presence)

Selected because biodiversity is a key indicator of forest ecosystem health, and monitoring fauna can inform conservation strategies important to owners.

3. Overview of ESS Indicators

Tiemann and Ring (2022) highlight the critical role of forests in providing a diverse range of ESS, emphasizing their relevance for biodiversity and human well-being. However, it underscores the pressing challenges facing European forests, including deforestation, fragmentation, and the impacts of changing climatic conditions. Tiemann and Ring (2022) emphasize that current assessments of FESs often prioritize timber production, neglecting other equally important services. To address this, the authors propose a systematic approach for assessing FESs using biophysical indicators. Their objective is to promote the use of forest function mapping, a valuable planning tool in Central European forestry, to identify and map forest areas crucial for protection and recreation. This approach is integrated with the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES 5.2) developed by Haines-Young, R. (2023) to ensure a comprehensive assessment. The authors focus on various ESS like - groundwater for drinking purposes, timber provision, global climate regulation, local air pollution reduction, recreation, and education and training. For each of these ESS, they propose indicators that cover their potential, supply, demand, and flow. The article provides insights into possible measurement methods, units of measurement, and data sources necessary for applying these indicators effectively. Importantly, the article emphasizes the need for transparent and reproducible assessment processes. It also acknowledges that while many indicators have the potential to provide scientifically sound results regarding the quantity of FESs, challenges remain, particularly in assessing the supply of groundwater for drinking purposes, and local air pollution reduction.

In conclusion, the article highlights the timeliness and relevance of biophysical assessment of FESs. It argues that such assessments can benefit both public and private forest owners and governmental organizations by improving SFM and guiding policy decisions. However, the article highlighted the importance of continued research and case study applications to refine and further develop the proposed indicators, ensuring their practicality and effectiveness in real-world forest conservation and management efforts.

3.1. Review of Existing Tools, Data, and Methodologies for ESS Indicators

Spain hosts a diverse ecosystem of digital tools and platforms aimed at assessing and managing the ESS, developed by public institutions, regional authorities, research centers, and private organizations. In the context of Task 3.4, which seeks to link forest management units with ecosystem service indicators and integrate these into PEFC Spain's certification system, a comprehensive review of these existing tools and methodologies is essential (Table 1).

At the national level, guideline like green infrastructure, developed by the Spanish government, support strategic planning and ESS assessment across landscapes. Regionally, SITxell provides territorial planning support in Catalonia by integrating ecological and socio-economic criteria. Forestry Laboratory, a research-based initiative, offers tools and datasets for monitoring forest-specific ESS, such as carbon sequestration and biodiversity indicators. Additionally, platforms like ForESMap and InstaMap enable enhanced spatial analysis and visualization of ESS data, in regional forest contexts.

At the international level, tools such as InVEST, CICES, and TEEB offer standardized methodologies for ESS classification, economic valuation, and impact modeling. These tools complement Spanish initiatives by providing globally recognized indicator frameworks and support for integrating biodiversity, soil, and climatological variables into ESS models.

The review of existing ESS also considered the data sources and methodologies used by these platforms, which commonly rely on remote sensing, ecological modeling, citizen science inputs, and institutional databases. Climatological and biodiversity-related variables

are often derived from national and EU-wide platforms or collected via participatory monitoring. Soil-related information is generally provided by institutional research centers or landowners themselves. These variables feed into existing ESS models, often requiring calculation adjustments and transformation into formats that can be easily understood and visualized by end users. A detailed overview of the existing ESS tools is presented in Table 1.

This review of existing ESS tools from Task 3.4 provided valuable insights for Pilot 4, an ongoing task focused on further developing an AI-powered ESS tool called the *Forest Ecosystem Services Analysis Tool*¹. AI-powered ESS tool aims to enhance the accessibility, interoperability, and usability of existing ESS within the scheme, serving forest owners, managers, and decision-makers. It will be further refined and presented as part of the WP5 deliverable. Additionally, the AI-powered ESS tool has already been tested by the forest owners' consortium, who responded positively and expressed their appreciation for the concept. The forest owners also offered suggestions for improvements, which are currently under integration for the improvement of the tool.

Table 1. Review of existing ESS tools.

Tool Name	Organization	Country/Region	Key ESS Covered	Link
1.InVEST	Natural Capital Project	International	Carbon, Timber, Water, Recreation, Biodiversity, Pollination, Scenic Quality, Habitat Quality	Link
2.ESTIMAP	European Commission JRC	EU	Pollination, Coastal Protection, Water Quality, Soil Retention, Recreation	Link
3.Green Infrastructure	Spanish Government	Spain	Water, Soil, Carbon, Biodiversity, Climate, Habitat Connectivity	Link
4.SITxell	Diputació de Barcelona	Spain (Barcelona)	Water, Timber, Carbon, Air, Soil, Pollination, Recreation, Biodiversity, Cultural Services	Link

¹ <https://frabjous-clafoutis-74d972.netlify.app/>

5.Forestry Laboratory	CREAF	Spain (Catalonia)	Carbon, Soil, Water, Timber, Fauna, Erosion Mitigation	Link
6.ForESMap	Agresta S. Coop.	Spain	Wood Production	Link
7.InstaMap	ICGC	Spain (Catalonia)	Carbon, Water, Soil, Biodiversity, Flood Control, Recreation, Timber	Link
8.FOREStime	CREAF, CTFC, OCCC	Spain (Catalonia)	Carbon Sink, Water, Wood, Mushroom Production, Erosion Control	Link
9.REDIAM	Junta de Andalucía	Spain (Andalusia)	Carbon, Soil, Water, Pollination, Cork, Timber, Recreation, Fire Risk, Biodiversity	Link
10.LIFE+ Ordunte Sostenible	Diputación Foral de Bizkaia	Spain (Basque Country)	Carbon, Biodiversity, Water, Recreation, Erosion	Link
11.VANE	Ministry for Ecological Transition (Spain)	Spain	Carbon, Food, Soil Fertility, Biodiversity, Pollination, Recreation	Link
12.FSC ES Impact Tool	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)	International	Carbon, Soil, Biodiversity, Water, Recreation	Link
13.FSC Forest Carbon Monitoring Tool	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)	International	Carbon sequestration, Climate regulation	Link
14.Environmental Externalities Accounting Tool (EX-ACT)	FAO	International	Carbon, Climate mitigation, Land-use change, Soil fertility	Link
15. ARIES	Basque Centre for Climate Change (BC3)	International	Water, Carbon, Soil, Biodiversity, Food, Flood risk mitigation, Recreation	Link

16.The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB)	UNEP, EC, and partners	International	All categories depend on project context	Link
17.Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES)	European Environment Agency	International	Provisioning, Regulation & maintenance, Cultural services	Link

3.2. Indicators of Selected ESS

With the importance of ESS indicators emphasized by Tiemann and Ring (2022), and drawing from the ForEScale (Banqué et al., 2017) and ForESMap (Banqué et al., 2016) projects, the commonly used indicators of ESS have been defined. In this section, we present the selected ESS indicators in Table 2.

Table 2. Selected ESS and their indicators (ForEScale and ForESMap projects; Laboratori Forestal Català, 2021).

Type of ESS	Data classification	Data Collection Year	ESS Indicators	ESS Explanation	Unit
Provisioning	Dynamic Data	1990 - 2015	Mushroom Production	Difference on the estimated production of edible mushrooms.	kg/ha/year
Provisioning	Dynamic Data	1990 - 2015	Exported Water (Blue water)	The amount of water that is available for human use after being filtered and regulated by forest ecosystems.	L/m ² /year

Regulating	Static Data	1990-2000	Carbon Sequestration	Forest carbon sink capacity.	t/ha/year
Regulating	Static Data	1975 - 2007	Soil Organic Carbon	Forest soil organic carbon stock.	t/ha
Regulating	Dynamic Data	1990 - 2015	Erosion Mitigation	Difference on the amount of soil erosion avoided by vegetation (tree and shrub canopies).	t/ha/year
Cultural	Static Data	2012-2014	Fauna observation (Animal presence)	Animal species observations obtained from to Catalan Ornithology Institute – ICO.	count

These specific indicators are to assess and monitor the provision and regulation of ESS, as well as the significance of ecosystems in Catalonia for cultural activities and biodiversity conservation.

3.3. Digitalized ESS – Example of Forestry Laboratory

With the increase of new technologies, artificial intelligence, and digital tools, the need for the digitalization of ESS has become increasingly evident. At CREAM, we have undertaken the digitalization of ESS for the Catalonia, Spain. To support and guide other regions in this process, we developed the replication guideline of CREAM's Forestry Laboratory as a reference platform. The Catalan Forestry Laboratory - Laboratori Forestal Català (Forestry Laboratory)² is a joint initiative by CREAM and the Forest Science and Technology Center of

² https://laboratoriforestal.cream.cat/fes_app/

Catalonia (CTFC) that initiated in 2019. It aims to make forest-related data accessible for both experts and the public, offering resources like forest maps, data downloads, and interactive tools. Designed for research, education, and administrative use, it supports the understanding and management of Catalonia's forests through processed, reliable datasets and visual tools.

The ESS data in the Forestry Laboratory has been shown in the section of Forest Ecosystem Services App (FES App). The FES App offers insights into forest ecosystem services across Catalonia, presenting information in two formats: static and dynamic. Static data represents ESS evaluated at a single point in time using various sources and models, which may differ for each service. Dynamic data, on the other hand, includes services calculated based on data and sample plots from the Spanish National Forest Inventory (NFI) across its versions (NFI2, NFI3, and NFI4), as well as the changes observed between these versions.

The digitization of ESS involves a comprehensive, multi-step process that transforms complex environmental data into accessible, visual, and user-friendly digital tools. This process begins with the identification of the ESS to be assessed, meaning, selecting which ESS will be shown in the tool. It also involves deciding how detailed the information should be in terms of scale of digitalizing the ESS (for example, showing ESS data for small 1 km² forest plots or for larger areas like municipalities or protected zones) and time (such as using data from one specific year, or comparing different years to see changes over time). Moreover, it is important to define who will be using the tool—such as researchers, forest owners/managers, or decision-makers—so that the design, language, and functions are easy for the users to understand and use. Once this basic information is defined, the next step is data acquisition and preprocessing, which involves collecting both static datasets (derived from existing sources at a single time point) and dynamic datasets (typically generated from long-term forest inventories such as NFI2, NFI3, and NFI4). Overall, this digitization framework enables users to visualize ESS data effectively while supporting data-driven decision-making for sustainable landscape planning and environmental conservation.

4. Overview of PEFC Spain

PEFC Spain is a non-governmental, non-profit organization that promotes and disseminates Sustainable Forest Management through forest certification and the chain of custody certification for forest products. This contributes to environmental and biodiversity conservation, while also fostering the social economy, circularity, and sustainable development.

Founded 1999, PEFC Spain is part of PEFC International, the world's largest forest certification system. It works with forest owners and managers, public administrations, companies, and civil society to ensure forest sustainability that delivers ecological, social, and economic benefits for all.

PEFC certification in Spain consists of two main components:

- **Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) Certification:** Ensures that forests are managed in a way that maintains their biodiversity, productivity, and regeneration capacity, while meeting ecological, economic, and social criteria.
- **Chain of Custody (CdC) Certification:** Guarantees the traceability of forest products from their origin in sustainably managed forests to the final consumer.

In Spain, by the end of 2024, the certified forest area exceeded 2.810.000 hectares. All of this forest land supplied sustainably sourced products to almost 1.800 companies, which were also certified through the CdC certification.

In summary, PEFC Spain plays a key role in promoting sustainable forest management across the country, contributing to environmental conservation, rural development, and the green economy.

4.1. PEFC Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) System

The core document that underpins the certification of Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) in Spain is the UNE Standard 162.002 on Sustainable Forest Management. This standard is developed through a participatory process involving all stakeholders with an interest in forest management in Spain, including:

- Forest owners
- Private companies and industry
- Public administrations
- The scientific and technological community
- Workers and trade unions
- Women
- Youth
- NGOs

The participation of these diverse sectors of society democratizes the process and ensures transparency. Furthermore, it allows the standard to follow a bottom-up approach, adapting to the realities of the national territory and the needs of the population.

All stakeholders take part in the drafting of the standard and collectively agree on what will serve as the fundamental basis for Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) in Spain. These are the six SFM criteria:

- **Criterion 1:** Maintenance and appropriate enhancement of forest resources and their contribution to the global carbon cycle.
- **Criterion 2:** Maintenance and enhancement of forest ecosystem health and vitality.
- **Criterion 3:** Maintenance and enhancement of the productive functions of forests (wood and other forest products).

- **Criterion 4:** Maintenance, conservation, and appropriate enhancement of biological diversity in forest ecosystems.
- **Criterion 5:** Maintenance and appropriate enhancement of the protective functions in forest management (mainly soil and water).
- **Criterion 6:** Maintenance of other socio-economic functions and conditions.

Each of these criteria includes a set of indicators to assess the performance of forest management against a specific criterion. These indicators are checked in what is often referred to as a management plan, a document that sets out the planning of future actions that will take place in each forest management unit (FMU) during the life of the plan. On the other hand, an independent third party (certification body) is the entity in charge of auditing the content of the management plans, and of visiting the FMU to ensure that the actions taking place in the FMU are aligned with and help to meet the objectives set out in the management plan.

5. Methodology

The assessment of ESS has been developed using geographical data from PEFC-certified FMUs, facilitated by Ens Català Sol·licitant de la Certificació Forestal PEFC (ENSCAT), combined with ESS data provided by Forestry Laboratory, as explained respectively in Sections 3.2 and 4. ENSCAT is the entity representing the PEFC certificate at the regional level. The area covered by ENSCAT, as in the rest of the national territory, varies over time; therefore, the forests that are part of the certified entity are not constant. A collaborative effort between ENSCAT and PEFC Spain was necessary to update this cartography. As a result, the shapefile format cartography of the area certified under the PEFC scheme as of January 30, 2025, was obtained. This integration provides specific information for each PEFC-certified sustainable FMU and its corresponding ESS values. With this, the goal of the Task 3.4 is to develop a system for PEFC Spain to communicate with forest owners, managers, and end users, displaying the calculated ESS values for each FMU. This will

provide forest owners, managers, and end users with clear information on how certified forests contribute to various ESS.

Methodological steps are the following:

I. Geospatial Data Collection:

- ENSCAT provided the geographical boundaries and spatial characteristics of PEFC-certified sustainable FMUs.

II. ESS Data Collection:

- The selected ESS (such as carbon sequestration, mushroom production, exported water, etc.) were compiled from the Forestry Laboratory and stored as a GeoPackage file to facilitate further analysis and use.
- These datasets of selected ESS include statistical analysis, remote sensing, field surveys, and ecological modeling (please refer to Section 3.2 and 3.3. for more details).

III. Data Integration & Spatial Analysis:

- The geographical data from ENSCAT was overlaid with the ESS data from the Forestry Laboratory using GIS-based tools and R Studio.
- RStudio was used not only for spatial analysis but also to develop an automated script that allows PEFC Spain to update the ESS platform continuously. This automation ensures that project data can be refreshed regularly even after the project ends, with minimal manual effort, facilitating ongoing communication and transparency with forest owners and other stakeholders.
- Spatial analysis techniques were applied to quantify ESS values at the FMU level, ensuring that each forest area was assessed based on its unique ecological characteristics.

IV. ESS Valuation & Interpretation:

- By integrating these two datasets, the study identified specific ESS information and benefits provided by each PEFC-certified sustainable FMU.

6. Results

6.1. Linking Each FMU with Indicators of ESS – Assessment

The following results are obtained from the integration of data from PEFC-certified sustainable FMUs in Catalonia, with ESS values provided by the Forestry Laboratory. These results include spatially distributed assessments of ESS, offering a detailed evaluation of the contributions made by these certified forests.

I. Mushroom Production

Figure 3 highlights that the vast majority of PEFC-certified FMUs are located in areas with relatively low potential for edible mushroom production (between 0 and 1.5 kg per hectare per year). However, on average, the mushroom production in kg per hectare per year across all FMUs is 5.80 kg/ha/year. It is important to note that mushroom production in the natural environment is highly dependent on the meteorological year. In the case of the data from the Forestry Laboratory of Catalonia (Miguel et al., 2014), the model takes into account meteorological variables such as maximum, average, and minimum temperatures, as well as precipitation between August and December.

When comparing the average mushroom production value obtained in the certified area with the average value of the rest of the region, it is observed that the latter is 0.14. These results suggest that, on average, PEFC-certified areas would potentially yield more than 5.5 kg more mushrooms per hectare per year than the rest of the region.

Figure 3. Map of estimated potential mushroom production values for each PEFC - certified FMU in the region of Catalonia.

II. Exported Water (Blue water)

Regarding the difference in exported water (for the calculation of this value, the difference between the blue water/precipitation ratios is made with the corresponding forest data from NFI4 and NFI2). This difference is calculated assuming that precipitation is constant; therefore, negative values of blue water indicate a greater amount of green water in the system. In other words, there is a higher amount of water used by the plants.

As observed in the map in Figure 4, most of the PEFC-certified area is characterized by negative values for exported water, which would imply that the forest ecosystems within the boundaries of the PEFC-certified area make a more optimal use of water resources through SFM, something crucial in Mediterranean environments prone to increasingly frequent drought events.

Figure 4. Map of estimated potential exported water values for each PEFC – certified FMU in the region of Catalonia.

III. Carbon Sequestration

Regarding carbon sequestration, it is observed that the vast majority of PEFC-certified FMUs fall within the potential carbon fixation range of 0 to 2 t/ha per year, with an average of 0.98 t/ha per year shown in figure 5. Considering that the PEFC-certified area in Catalonia totals 267,895 hectares, the potential contribution of PEFC forests to carbon sequestration in the Catalonian region is estimated to be around 262,537 tons of C per year. On the other hand, the average potential carbon sequestration in the rest of the region, excluding the certified area, is 0.15 t/ha per year, which would imply that the certified area is considerably higher in terms of carbon fixation. In this way, the important role of SFM and PEFC certification in contributing to ESS is highlighted.

Despite all of the above, it is necessary to use this information while considering its limitations. However, it is again believed that having this baseline information can be very enlightening for the development of future studies, as well as regional policies focused on

carbon emissions and how to approach forestry to maximize the carbon sink effect of forests.

Figure 5. Map of estimated potential carbon sequestration values for each PEFC – certified FMU in the region of Catalonia.

IV. Soil Organic Carbon

Figure 6 details the potential amount of organic carbon stored in the soil of each PEFC-certified FMU. The total is 120,913.32 t C, with an average value of 63.11 t C/ha. This value is significantly higher than that obtained from non-certified PEFC areas in Catalonia (20.08 t/ha). This would indicate that, potentially, within the certified area, there is more than 40 t/ha more organic carbon stored in the soil. This has direct implications for soil ecosystems, their intrinsic biodiversity, and health, as a higher amount of organic carbon in the soil would imply higher biodiversity indices in soil ecosystems (FAO, 2017).

Figure 6. Map of estimated potential soil organic carbon values for each PEFC – certified FMU in the region of Catalonia.

V. Erosion Mitigation

The erosion mitigated by vegetation cover (Figure 7) shows that a large portion of PEFC-certified UGFs prevent soil losses of between 5 and 25 tons per hectare per year, with an average value of 7.62 t/ha per year. In contrast, the average value in the rest of the region's surface is only 3.88 t/ha per year. Once again, it is observed that, on average, PEFC-certified FMU areas contribute to erosion mitigation as a result of proper forest management. Despite the potential usefulness of this information, the calculation method—based on the difference between the results obtained from NFI4 and NFI2—is considered not only overly static but also outdated. Since the completion of NFI4, vegetation may have undergone substantial changes that would significantly alter the results. Therefore, the calculation of this ecosystem service should be subject to the availability of more up-to-date vegetation cover data, as unlike other ESS, it does not allow for the evaluation of a trend.

Figure 7. Map of estimated potential erosion mitigation values for each PEFC – certified FMU in the region of Catalonia.

VI. Fauna observation (Animal presence)

In relation to the bird observations obtained from the Catalan Institute of Ornithology, the vast majority of FMUs have values between 0 and 5 (Figure 8). It is important to highlight that this data depends on contributions made by volunteer experts in ornithology. In other words, low sighting values do not necessarily indicate a low presence of birdlife in the ecosystems. Nonetheless, it is observed that within the PEFC-certified area, the average potential value for bird sightings is 2.66, compared to the average value of 0.32 found outside the certified area. Taking all of the above into account and understanding what this variable implies, it is considered an adequate initial approximation for assessing species richness and other parameters that allow for quantifying biodiversity within the boundaries of sustainably managed areas.

Figure 8. Map of estimated animal presence values for each PEFC – certified FMU in the region of Catalonia.

6.2. ESS Reporting and Visualization through PEFC Spain ESS Platform

All the information generated within the scope of the development of Task 3.4, as previously described, has been integrated into a freely accessible platform for consulting the ESS selected within the PEFC-certified area in Catalonia. The software PowerBI has been used to create the platform, the PEFC Spain ESS platform³ allows for dynamic handling of a large number of databases, the main dashboard shown in figure 9.

³ <https://pefc.es/que-hacemos/nuestro-impacto-colectivo/nuestros-proyectos/digimedfor>

Portal de servicios ecosistémicos de los bosques PEFC en Cataluña

¿Qué puedes encontrar en este portal?

En el marco del Proyecto DigiMedFor PEFC España ofrece una visión detallada de los valores potenciales de los servicios ecosistémicos proporcionados por los bosques gestionados bajo la certificación PEFC en la región de Catalunya. Gracias al uso de avanzados modelos de cálculo, se han estimado diversos beneficios que estos ecosistemas aportan al medio ambiente y a la sociedad.

¿Para qué?

Este portal permite vincular la Gestión Forestal Sostenible certificada por PEFC con indicadores clave sobre servicios ecosistémicos, para facilitar el acceso a una información clara, trazable y útil, tanto para propietarios forestales, como para el público en general

¿Qué información sobre servicios ecosistémicos se muestra?

Ofrece datos calculados sobre determinados servicios ecosistémicos: fijación de carbono, producción de setas, presencia de avifauna y agua exportada.

¿Cómo se obtiene esta información?

El cálculo es el resultado de la aplicación de los modelos de cálculo de los citados servicios ecosistémicos desarrollados por el Laboratori Forestal Català cruzados con la cartografía de las Unidades de Gestión Forestal (UGF) certificadas bajo el esquema PEFC cedidos por ENSCAT - Ens Català Sol·licitant de la Certificació Forestal PEFC a fecha 30/01/2025.

*Para más información acerca de la metodología de cálculo de los servicios ecosistémicos visitar (https://laboratoriforestal.creaf.cat/fes_app/)

Figure 9. Interface of the PEFC Spain ESS Platform for ESS Reporting and Visualization.

Through this portal, it is possible to easily check the potential contribution of PEFC forests to each of the ESS selected for analysis. Additionally, the platform allows the application of different filters to display values at the FMU scale, also showing the corresponding values for the province or municipality in which each forest is located, so that a comparison of these values can be made. The platform presents information in dashboards or thematic panels, with one panel for each ecosystem service, as shown in the example in figure 10.

Figure 10. Dashboard for Carbon Sequestration Calculation on the PEFC ESS Portal for Catalonia's Forests.

As shown in Figure 10, on the left side of the dashboard, there is a section with the available filters, among which we find the forest or FMU, the province, and the municipality in question. When activating these filters, the graph will update, along with the values displayed in the green box located on the right. Additionally, basic information explaining the definitions of each listed ESS is provided below the graph.

In this way, it is possible to easily make comparisons between provinces, municipalities, or forests. On the other hand, there is a small information button located at the top right of each navigation button, through which an explanatory text about each ecosystem service is displayed.

As outlined in sections 4 and 4.1, by the end of 2024, the certified forest area in Spain amounted to 2.810.733 hectares. This creates a network of forest landowners, forest managers, local entities, and other stakeholders who contribute to SFM while promoting and strengthening rural development and the green economy. Spain's total wooded forest area is approximately 19.200.000 hectares, meaning that 14.6% of this area is certified. Specifically in Catalonia, the PEFC-certified area reached 278.516 hectares. Given that the total forest area in Catalonia stands at 1.582.057 hectares, the certified area represents 17,6 % of the region's wooded forest land. This places Catalonia above the national average in

terms of certified forest area, highlighting the region’s strong commitment to SFM and the sound planning of Catalonia’s forests.

Moreover, this platform specifically highlights the potential contribution of certified forests to various ESS compared to non-certified forests, precisely through SFM.

7. Validation and End User Testing

7.1. Test 1: Forest Owners’ Understanding and Acceptance in Catalonia

As part of the pilot testing activities under Task 3.4, we engaged directly with forest owners—key stakeholders from the Forestry Consortium of Catalonia (CFC)⁴—to evaluate their understanding and perceptions of the newly developed platform. The developed PEFC Spain ESS Platform⁵ was initially shared with the participants via email, along with a request for feedback and comments.

Following their review, the forest owners expressed interest in discussing the platform’s usability during an online meeting to explore it collaboratively. Accordingly, the meeting held on 29th March 2025 provided an opportunity to present the tool interactively and gather direct feedback from the two forest owners who joined the meeting.

During the meeting, the forest owners shared their valuable comments, concerns as well as constructive remarks, including:

At the beginning of the meeting, forest owners expressed difficulty in understanding the overall concept of the platform. We explained that the ESS platform is based on the outcomes of the Forestry Laboratory, that Forestry Laboratory previously developed by CREAM in collaboration with other project partners. Specifically, the ESS platform integrates

⁴ [Consorci Forestal de Catalunya](#)

⁵ <https://pefc.es/que-hacemos/nuestro-impacto-colectivo/nuestros-proyectos/digimedfor>

data from the Forestry Laboratory with the geographical locations of PEFC certified FMUs in Catalonia to provide an estimation of ESS values.

During the discussion, forest owners asked for detailed information about the data sources used. We clarified that the platform incorporates both static and dynamic data. The dynamic data comes from the difference from NFI2 - NFI4 (1990 - 2015) while static datasets include broader environmental and forest-related indicators which differ in data collection years. However, forest owners raised concerns that these data sources are outdated and do not reflect the current ESS values. Also, they indicated that the use of NFI data limits the accuracy and relevance of the results presented.

We acknowledged their concerns and emphasized that this platform represents a first step in the digitalization of ESS information. Due to the scope and time constraints of the DigiMedFor project, we were unable to conduct new fieldwork to obtain real-time ESS data. Nonetheless, the platform aims to demonstrate how certified forests contribute to ESS provision, using existing datasets as a starting point. As a result of their feedback, we agreed to update the PEFC Spain ESS platform for data year and source concern in order to provide transparent information.

Another important point raised by the forest owners was regarding the spatial scale of data presentation. They expressed concern about displaying ESS estimates at the FMU level, especially since the data is not current. They suggested aggregating data at a minimum municipal level. We agreed to remove the FMU level display from the platform and confirmed this decision during the meeting.

With this, the discussion also highlighted concerns about the way ESS averages are compared between certified and non-certified forests. The forest owners emphasized that presenting these averages without contextualizing the number of management units per municipality can be misleading. They recommended including a section that shows the number of management units considered per area, to enhance the clarity and accuracy of the data presented. We will collaborate with PEFC Spain to explore how best to address this issue in future iterations of the platform.

Additionally, the forest owners proposed a potential future improvement: developing a feature that allows forest owners to input their forest management unit number to access

ESS information specific to their property. While we recognized the value of this idea, we clarified that it is beyond the current scope of Task 3.4. However, we have taken note of the proposal and will explore its feasibility in the future.

At the conclusion of the meeting, forest owners shared that they did not find the tool user-friendly in its current form. While we understood their frustration, we reiterated that the purpose of Task 3.4 is to showcase the potential contribution of certified forests to ESS, based on the theory that forest certification supports sustainability, which in turn enhances ESS provision. Indeed, the initial findings from the PEFC Spain ESS platform suggest that certified forests tend to provide higher average ESS values than non-certified ones.

However, we acknowledge that several aspects of the platform require further refinement. Based on the feedback from this meeting, we have identified several pending actions for improvement, particularly regarding data transparency, visualization scale, and contextualization of averages.

Following the evaluation and testing of the platform with key stakeholders - forest owners, the following improvements have been implemented on the platform:

- Update the PEFC Spain ESS platform to display the data year and source for each ESS.
- Remove data at the FMU level and show only municipal-level data, including the number of FMUs per municipality.
- Enhance the information box in the platform for comparing and averaging ESS data to better highlight objectives and provide a clearer comparison between certified and non-certified forest areas.

Finally, the collaboratively developed improvements to the PEFC Spain ESS Platform were shared with all stakeholders in the form of a survey, aiming to gather final feedback, ensure a clear understanding of the communicated ESS data, and support sensitivity testing.

7.2. Test 2: End Users' Sensitivity to Ecosystem Services

The sensitivity test aims to evaluate end users' understanding of the communicated ESS data, their perception of the platform's usability, and their level of engagement with the PEFC Spain ESS platform, which integrates ESS indicators. The test assesses how effectively the platform conveys the added value of sustainably managed forests through ESS data and explores users' comprehension, preferences, and potential influence on their behavior.

By linking each FMU with relevant ESS indicators through the platform, the objective is to present transparent, accessible, and easily understandable information to a broad range of end users –also referred to as stakeholders—including citizens, public institutions, businesses, and forestry experts. This visualization aims to highlight the intrinsic value of SFM by demonstrating how certified forests contribute more significantly to ESS compared to non-certified ones, thereby reinforcing the added value of certification from an environmental perspective.

7.2.1. User Feedback Survey Design

The survey consists of eight questions aimed at gathering user feedback. To ensure accessibility and inclusiveness, the questions were made available in three languages: English, Spanish, and Catalan. The full list of questions is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. User Feedback Survey – Usefulness and Clarity of ESS Information on the PEFC Spain ESS Platform.

#	Questions (EN)	Preguntas (ES)	(CA)	Responses
1	Personal Information Name and surname	Datos personales Nombre y apellido	Dades personals Nom i cognoms	Open answer
2	Organization Name	Nombre de la organización	Nom de l'organització	Open answer

3	How often do you visit the PEFC Spain website?	¿Con qué frecuencia visitas la página web de PEFC España?	¿Amb quina freqüència visites la pàgina web de PEFC Espanya?	<input type="checkbox"/> It is first time / Es la primera vez / És la primera vegada <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally (1–2 times/year) / Ocasionalmente (1–2 veces al año) / De tant en tant <input type="checkbox"/> Regularly (3+ times/year) / Regularmente (3 o más veces al año) / Regularment
4	Was the ecosystem services information on the platform easy to understand?	¿La información sobre servicios ecosistémicos en la plataforma te pareció fácil de entender?	¿La informació sobre serveis ecosistèmics a la plataforma et va semblar fàcil d'entendre?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very difficult / Muy difícil / Molt difícil <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat difficult / Algo difícil / Una mica difícil <input type="checkbox"/> Clear and understandable / Clara y comprensible / Clara i comprensible
5	Did this information add value to your understanding of sustainable forest management?	¿La información aportó valor a tu comprensión sobre la gestión forestal sostenible?	¿La informació va aportar valor a la teva comprensió sobre la gestió forestal sostenible?	<input type="checkbox"/> No added value / Sin valor añadido / Cap valor afegit <input type="checkbox"/> Moderate added value / Valor moderado / Valor moderat <input type="checkbox"/> High added value / Alto valor (me ayuda a tomar decisiones o comunicar) / Alt valor
6	Would this information influence your decisions (e.g., purchases, forest	¿Cree que esta información influiría en sus decisiones (p. ej.,	¿Creus que aquesta informació influiria en les teves decisions (per	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all / No lo creo / No ho crec <input type="checkbox"/> Somehow / Tal vez / Potser

	management, communication)?	compras, gestión forestal, comunicación)?	exemple, compres, gestió forestal, comunicació)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes, definitely / Sí, totalmente / Sí, totalment
7	What best describes your profile? (<i>Select all that apply</i>)	¿A qué perfil profesional pertenece? (<i>Puede marcar más de una opción</i>)	¿A quin perfil professional pertany? (<i>Pot marcar més d'una opció</i>)	<input type="checkbox"/> Forest owner / Propietario/a forestal / Propietari/ària forestal <input type="checkbox"/> Forest manager / Gestor/a forestal <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental expert / Experto/a en medio ambiente / Expert/a en medi ambient <input type="checkbox"/> Researcher or Academician / Investigador/a o académico/a <input type="checkbox"/> Public entity worker / Trabajador/a de entidad pública / Treballador/a d'una entitat pública <input type="checkbox"/> General public / Ciudadano/a / Ciutadà/ana <input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____
8	What would you improve or add to the platform to make it more useful?	¿Qué mejorarías o añadirías a la plataforma para que le resulte más útil?	Què milloraries o afegiries a la plataforma perquè et resulti més útil?	(<i>Open answer / Respuesta abierta</i>)

7.2.2. Survey Objectives and Focus

The main objective of the survey was to evaluate the usability and clarity of the PEFC Spain ESS Platform. Specifically, it aimed to communicate the evaluated ESS for Catalonia, Spain and access whether users could easily understand the content and structure of the platform.

The additional objectives of the survey are as follows:

- Raise awareness and interest in ESS values
- Promote the use and visual clarity of the ESS platform
- Measure the perceived credibility and practical usefulness of the information provided
- Explore the overall user experience and its relevance to professional or academic interests.

7.2.3. Methodology of User Feedback Survey

The survey⁶ was distributed to over 500 users to assess the usability of the PEFC Spain ESS platform. The selection of participants was based on their relevant profiles and expertise. Initially, the survey was shared with the Forest Owners Consortium (CFC), internal CREAM staff specialized in ecology and ESS, and the PEFC Spain ESS Working Group. Additionally, it was circulated among DigiMedFor project partners.

To broaden the reach, the survey was also sent to professionals and organizations with relevant backgrounds, including ESS experts, forestry and ESS-focused universities, and members of Forest Engineering Association.

Beyond these targeted groups, the survey link was made publicly available through LinkedIn⁷ and Survey Circle⁸ to maximize participation.

7.2.4. Survey Key Findings

A total of 28 responses were collected through the Google Forms survey. The feedback provides valuable insights into users' perceptions of the PEFC Spain ESS Platform. The responses to each question excluding personal data, are summarized below.

⁶ <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSexOxrkEUTyYyIQurgBbxycXEIBB7E2s5aB7cb1A0SOX6zzyw/viewform?usp=preview>

⁷ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/burcu-berk-72733bba_trilingual-survey-link-escaten-https-activity-7329096078790758400-J2oW?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABIShU8BnAXXoNwNGselNhToqMo1OAJTwm0

⁸ <https://www.surveycircle.com/es/survey/M6T5KL/>

Q1. Respondent Profile

The answers mostly varied between Environmental Experts (26%) and Researchers (24%), followed by Forest Managers (16%) and Forest Owners (13%). Additionally, there were 11% responses from Citizens/Public, 8% from Public Entity Workers, and 2% working in the forest industry. Details with approximate counts are shown in figure 11.

Figure 11. Profile of survey respondents by role.

Q2. Website Usage

The majority of respondents (19 out of 28) are first-time visitors to the PEFC Spain website, suggesting that the website is attracting new users but may still have limited repeat engagement. A smaller group of users (5 users) visit the site occasionally, indicating some level of ongoing interest or need for periodic information. Meanwhile, only 4 users reported regular visits, which suggests that a core group of dedicated users relies on the website frequently. This distribution highlights an opportunity for PEFC Spain to develop strategies to increase user retention and encourage more frequent visits for the ESS platform. Details are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Frequency of visits to the PEFC Spain website among survey respondents.

Q3. Understanding of ESS Information

Results indicated that 78.6% of respondents (22 out of 28) found the information clear and understandable. In contrast, 21.4% (6 respondents) indicated that they found it somewhat difficult to understand, suggesting room for improvement in making the content more accessible or user-friendly. The details are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. User perception of understanding the ESS information on PEFC Spain website

Q4. Added Value to Understanding SFM

The majority of users, 64.3% (18 respondents), indicated that the information added “moderate” value to their understanding of SFM. Additionally, 25% (7 respondents) reported a high added value, while 10.7% (3 respondents) found no added value. Details are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. User responses on whether the information added value to their understanding of SFM.

The survey results regarding the added value of the information for understanding SFM indicate that most participants found the ESS content beneficial, suggesting it effectively enhanced their knowledge.

Q5. Influence of PEFC Spain ESS Platform on Decision-Making

Results showed that, over half of the respondents (57.1% - 16 respondents) indicated the information from the PEFC Spain ESS platform as somewhat influential on their forest management decisions or communications, mentioning that the platform plays a meaningful role in guiding user actions. Nearly one-fifth (17.9% - 5 respondents) of users are fully convinced of the platform's influence, demonstrating that for a notable portion of respondents, the platform significantly impacts their decision-making.

However, it is important to highlight that a quarter of users (25% - 7 respondents) reported that the platform did not influence their decisions at all. This suggests that while the platform is valuable to many, there remains a considerable group for whom the information may lack sufficient relevance, clarity, or practical applicability. This gap points to an opportunity for the PEFC Spain ESS platform to strengthen its content or user engagement strategies to better support and influence a broader range of users in their decision-making processes. Details are shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Influence of PEFC Spain ESS Platform Information on User Decision-Making.

Q5. User Suggestions for Improving the PEFC Spain ESS Platform

Out of the 17 responses, approximately 23.5% indicated positive comments praising the platform’s current state, noting its usefulness and good usability. However, the majority, about 76.5%—offered constructive suggestions for improvement, highlighting opportunities to enhance content clarity, visualization, multilingual support, interface design, and added features to increase the platform’s overall usefulness and accessibility.

A closer look at the suggested improvements is provided below:

Overall positive feedback:

Several users expressed that the platform was well-prepared, interesting, useful, and easy to use. Some mentioned good usability and intuitive design.

Areas for improvement identified:

i. Content clarity:

- Some users found descriptions valuable but too long or complex, suggesting shorter summaries or clearer explanations.
- Users suggested adding a summary of methodologies for each ESS and more descriptive information for users less familiar with the topic.

ii. Comparative data and visualization enhancements:

- Several respondents requested more direct comparisons between certified and non-certified forest areas, including visual comparisons of ESS.
- Suggestions include adding baseline references, comparison by forest type, municipality, or province, and clearer visual indicators like percentage differences.
- One user recommended adding maps with modeled data to aid understanding and management.

iii. Language and accessibility:

- A user recommended adding English support to accommodate international users.
- Some users suggested making the platform more accessible and understandable for non-experts or those with limited forestry knowledge in order to contribute to their decision-making process.

iv. Additional content and features:

- A user suggested adding profiles of the DigiMedFor project or platform team to build trust and transparency.
- A user suggested including a catalog of certified products.
- A user indicated integrating socioeconomic data relevant to the region (e.g., Catalonia, Spain).
- Another user suggested creating modeling of forest management plan information.

v. User interface and usability tweaks:

- A user suggested improving certain UI elements, such as the central-colored bar, to add meaningful insights.

7.2.5. Overall Summary of Survey Results

The survey responses indicate that the PEFC Spain ESS Platform is generally perceived as a useful and well-prepared platform that adds value to users' understanding of sustainable forest management. Many users find the information clear, relevant, and presented in an intuitive way, which supports decision-making for a majority of respondents.

At the same time, feedback highlights important opportunities to improve the platform's impact and accessibility. Users commonly expressed the need for clearer, more concise content that can be easily understood by those with varying levels of forestry knowledge. Enhancing visual comparisons between certified and non-certified forest areas, including more dynamic and localized data visualizations such as maps and baseline references, would make the platform more engaging and insightful.

Finally, improving specific interface elements to more effectively communicate meaningful differences and results, as suggested, could further enhance the user experience. Overall, while the platform is valued for its strong foundation, these enhancements have the potential to significantly increase its practical relevance, stakeholder engagement, users' understanding of the provided ESS values, and influence on sustainable forest management – ultimately supporting the contribution of certified forests to ESS.

8. Digitalization and Certification

Guidelines for Replication Sites

8.1. Guidelines for ESS Digitalization: A Case Study of Forestry Laboratory by CREAM

The Forestry Laboratory, as detailed in Section 3.2, serves as a digital reference model for ESS integration. It combines spatial data, ecological indicators, and end-user communication strategies within a digital platform. By combining spatial datasets and ecological indicators, it demonstrates how digital innovation can bridge the gap between environmental data and actionable insights for sustainable forest management, policy and technical decision-making.

This guideline offers practical instructions for replication sites seeking to develop a similar platform for their national or regional needs. Moreover, this guideline focuses on translating the Forestry Laboratory's core approach into concrete, adaptable steps to facilitate successful implementation in new contexts. Additionally, each step includes general suggestions for replication sites.

This guideline aims to:

- Aggregate and analyze ESS data across multiple spatial and temporal scales.
- Equip decision-makers with practical tools to monitor, evaluate, and interpret ESS data.
- Support SFM and certification processes (e.g., PEFC).
- Enable policy development through the use of spatially explicit ESS indicators and trends.

8.1.1. Methodology of Digitalization of ESS

Step 1: Data Harmonization

Data harmonization is the process of standardizing data from multiple sources to ensure consistency and comparability across different datasets.

Forestry Laboratory has utilized the following harmonized datasets:

- The Forestry Laboratory uses National Forest Inventory (NFI) plots with ~1 km resolution and raster datasets with finer pixel sizes.
- To ensure consistency, all data is standardized to a 1 km resolution.
- Data is spatially aggregated within administrative units (municipal, regional).
- If fewer than 3 plots exist within a unit, the data will not be combined to maintain statistical integrity and ensure reliable results.

Suggestions for the Data Harmonization Process for the Replication Sites:

- Standardizing Spatial Resolution:
 - Convert all datasets to the same spatial resolution. For example, if you have field plot data at a 100-meter resolution and satellite imagery at 10-meter resolution, resample both datasets to a common resolution, such as 1 km², to ensure uniformity when analyzing them together.
- Aligning Coordinate Systems:
 - Ensure that all datasets are using the same coordinate reference system. If one dataset uses UTM (Universal Transverse Mercator) and another uses WGS84, you need to convert them into a single system so that spatial features (e.g., forest boundaries, observation points) align accurately.
- Matching Temporal Ranges:
 - Ensure that the datasets used cover comparable time periods. When working with datasets that do not overlap temporally – for example, a biodiversity dataset from 2010 to 2015 and a land cover dataset from 2018 to 2020 – you cannot simply choose a common year. In such cases, consider methods such

as interpolating one dataset to estimate values for the missing period, or selecting the closest possible time points while clearly acknowledging the temporal gap and any limitations this may introduce into the analysis.

- [Aggregating Data into Units:](#)
 - Group data based on administrative or ecological units. For example, if you have data at the national level, break it down into smaller regions, such as municipalities, watersheds, or FMUs, to make the data more relevant for local decision-making.

These steps help ensure that all datasets are compatible and ready for analysis, providing consistent, reliable information for ecosystem service evaluations.

Step 2: Data Sources

The quality of the data used in ESS platforms is critical. The Forestry Laboratory platform utilizes the following datasets:

- NFI (Spanish National Forest Inventory) – spatially explicit field data and covering multiple time points for comparison:
 - NFI 2 (1990–1992)
 - NFI 3 (2000–2001)
 - NFI 4 (2014–2017)
- MCSC (Catalonian Land Cover Map) – detailed land classification.
- ICO (Catalonian Ornithology Institute) – biodiversity and bird observation data.
- Peer-reviewed Research:
 - De Miguel et al. (2014)
 - De Cáceres et al. (2015)
 - Doblás-Miranda et al. (2013)

These sources provided both raw data and ESS indicators (For more info, see FORESCALE report, and Rocés-Díaz et al. 2018a, Rocés-Díaz et al. 2018b and Rocés-Díaz et al. 2021.)

Suggestions for Data Sources for the Replication Sites:

Additional data sources can be considered depending on local availability and the needs of the replication site:

- [Remote Sensing \(e.g., satellite images, drone data\)](#): Useful for capturing land cover, vegetation health, and changes over time at high resolution.
- [Biodiversity Data from national databases or local studies](#): These can include bird sightings, habitat maps, or species presence, which are valuable for ecological indicators.

These sources can be combined and analyzed using a Geographic Information System (GIS) to generate spatially explicit ESS indicators that support visualization, mapping, and decision-making.

Step 3: Spatial and Temporal Scales

In Forestry Laboratory, we selected both spatial and temporal scales for analyzing and visualizing ESS based on the data available. These scales were chosen to ensure that the analysis was relevant to different administrative or ecological units and allowed for detailed insights into forest ecosystems.

- [Temporal Scales in Forestry Laboratory:](#)

We worked with both static and dynamic temporal data:

- [Static Data](#): ESS calculated for a single time point using available models and datasets.
- [Dynamic Data](#): We used data from the NFI as mentioned in more detail in Step 2.

This approach enabled us to track changes in ESS over time, such as comparing different Dynamic data that allows us to study forest ecosystem dynamics and their evolution.

- [Spatial Scales in Forestry Laboratory:](#)

We chose various spatial scales based on the needs of the study. These included:

- [Local Scale](#): 1 km² grid cells or NFI plots, allowing fine-scale analysis of specific forest ecosystems.

- [Municipal Level](#): Data aggregated at the municipality level provided insights into ESS within local communities.
- [County Level](#): For larger regions, data were aggregated at the county level, which offered a broader perspective of ESS across the territory.
- [Province Level](#): We also looked at larger administrative units, aggregating data at the province level for a more extensive regional analysis.
- [Natural Interest Areas](#): Areas with recognized ecological value, such as protected forests or zones marked for conservation.
- [Special Protection Natural Areas](#): Regions with legal protection that were critical for monitoring ESS tied to biodiversity and conservation.
- [Natura 2000 Network](#): For sites within the European Union, we used the Natura 2000 network boundaries, which represent areas of conservation interest.
- [Polygon Files](#): Custom polygon files (e.g., shapefiles) were used to define specific regions of interest, allowing tailored analyses for designated forest zones.

[Suggestions for Spatial and Temporal Scales for Replication Sites](#)

For replication sites, the choice of spatial and temporal scales should be adapted based on the available data and the specific goals of the analysis. Adjusting the spatial and temporal scales to the local context will ensure meaningful and comparable ecosystem service evaluations across different replication sites.

Step 4: Defining ESS Indicators

Defining indicators is crucial for understanding the effects of scale in ecosystem service evaluations and the relationships between services. When replicating the Forestry Laboratory model, the selected indicators should be:

- [Quantifiable overtime](#): Indicators should be measurable over various temporal scales to detect changes in the provision of ESS.
- [Spatially explicit](#): Data should represent the geographical location of the service and be available for the defined spatial scale.

- [Scalable](#): Indicators should be adaptable to different spatial and temporal scales, as this enables flexibility in analysis at local, regional, or national levels.

[Key Considerations for Indicator Selection:](#)

- [Broad Coverage vs. Scale Sensitivity](#): While the goal of the Forestry Laboratory was to cover a wide range of ESS (please see the report of ForEsMap⁹), the replication projects might focus on fewer services to understand how the relationships between indicators change across scales.
- [Data Availability Across Scales](#): Some indicators (e.g., wood production, rural tourism, or biodiversity hotspots) might only be available at certain spatial scales, such as national or municipal levels. If data is unavailable for specific scales, those indicators cannot be used across all desired scales.

[Example indicators for Replication Sites:](#)

- [Biophysical Indicators](#): For example, the Forestry Laboratory used indicators like "water storage in canopy and soil" for hydrological services, or "biodiversity richness" for ecological services. Depending on the data availability and the focus of your project, you can choose similar indicators but ensure that the data is available across your spatial scales (local, municipal, or regional).
 - [For example](#): ESS indicators could include carbon sequestration in forest plots, soil erosion rate for land cover changes, and species diversity for forest health.
- [Explanatory Variables](#): Certain environmental variables (e.g., temperature, precipitation, or forest cover) can act as explanatory variables that help in understanding patterns in ESS.
 - [For instance](#), species richness (both tree and bird species) could explain patterns in biodiversity and ecosystem functionality.

By following these guidelines, you ensure that the indicators used in your project reflect the services accurately at different scales, enabling meaningful comparisons and robust analysis.

⁹ https://laboratoriforestal.creaf.cat/informe_forescale.pdf

Suggestions for ESS Indicator Selection for Replication Sites:

1. Choose bio-physical indicators that can be quantified over time and provide insight into the status and changes in ESS.
2. Make sure that the data for these indicators is available at the relevant spatial scales.
3. Select explanatory variables that help explain variations in ESS (e.g., forest cover or species richness).
4. Ensure scalability by selecting indicators that can be aggregated or disaggregated depending on the spatial unit.

Step 5: Data Integration and Analysis

After harmonizing the data and defining spatial and temporal scales, the next step is to integrate the datasets and extract meaningful ecosystem service (ESS) indicators.

- GIS Processing:
 - Use tools like QGIS or ArcGIS to process spatial data.
 - Aggregate information by selected spatial units (e.g., municipality, Natura 2000, custom polygons).
 - Combine layers such as land cover, forest type, and biodiversity zones to identify ESS patterns.
- Mathematical Models:
 - Apply scientific formulas or models to calculate ESS indicators:
 - Estimate carbon sequestration using forest biomass data.
 - Assess timber production from forest inventory data.
 - Derive biodiversity metrics from species observation databases.
- Temporal Analysis:
 - Compare datasets from different years to detect trends and changes in ESS.

- Use time series or change detection techniques to evaluate forest ecosystem dynamics.
- [Automation and Scripting:](#)
 - Use Python or R to automate data processing, especially useful for large-scale or repeated calculations.
 - Automating tasks ensure efficiency, consistency, and scalability.

Step 6: Visualization and Communication of Results

Once ESS indicators are calculated, results need to be clearly communicated to ensure they support decision-making, public awareness, and stakeholder engagement. The aim is to make complex data accessible and actionable.

[Forestry Laboratory Example:](#)

We developed an interactive online platform where users can explore ESS indicators across different spatial and temporal scales. The platform includes:

- Maps showing the spatial distribution of ESS such as carbon storage or biodiversity hotspots.
- Graphs presenting changes over time (e.g., forest dynamics, carbon sequestration trends).
- Downloadable reports summarizing key insights per administrative or ecological unit. You can explore the Forestry Laboratory visualization platform.¹⁰

[Suggestions for Visualization and Communication of Results for Replication Sites:](#)

You can adopt a similar approach using available GIS and data visualization tools.

- Use maps (static or interactive) to display ESS indicators spatially.
- Include charts to highlight trends or compare indicators between regions.
- Develop short summary reports with clear visuals, titles, and key takeaways tailored to different audiences.

¹⁰ https://laboratoriforestal.creaf.cat/fes_app/

- Consider web-based dashboards (using platforms like ArcGIS Online, Tableau, or Power BI) for interactive exploration.

Clear and engaging communication ensures that the ESS data can inform local planning, conservation, and FM in a meaningful way.

8.1.2. Average Cost Estimation for Developing and Maintaining a Forestry Laboratory Like Platform

Based on expert input from real life Forestry Laboratory development, the following provides an estimation of the qualified person and technical resource costs required for both the creation and maintenance phases of a similar digital platform:

[i. Creation Phase \(From Scratch\)](#)

Item	Details
Team Composition	2 people: • Backend/Data Developer (Full-time) • Frontend Support (Half-time)
Duration	6 months
Monthly Salary Range	€3,000 – €4,000
Total Personnel Cost	€36,000 – €48,000 (2 people × €3,000–€4,000 × 6 months)

[ii. Maintenance Phase \(Annually\)](#)

Item	Details
Team Composition	1 person (Full-time) for technical maintenance, updates, and basic user support
Monthly Salary Range	€3,000 – €4,000
Total Annual Cost	€36,000 – €48,000 (1 person × €3,000–€4,000 × 12 months)

[iii. Infrastructure Costs \(Annually\)](#)

Item	Details
Servers	2 mid-level servers for stability and backup
Monthly Cost	€150 – €250

Item	Details
Total Annual Cost	€1,800 – €3,000 (€150–€250 × 12 months)

8.1.3. Adapting the Forestry Laboratory Example for Local Contexts

Successful replication of ESS assessments depends on how well the methods and tools are adapted to local realities. In Forestry Laboratory, we learned that customization and participation are key to relevance and impact.

Key Actions:

- [Customize Indicators and Methods](#)
 - Adjust ESS indicators based on local ecosystem types, land use, and stakeholder priorities.
 - For example, in Mediterranean forests, water regulation and fire risk may be more relevant than in temperate zones—so the ESS indicators should reflect these realities.
 - Use locally available data sources (e.g., regional forest inventories, biodiversity surveys, community maps) and calibrate models accordingly.
- [Engage Local Stakeholders Early](#)
 - Involve local actors—such as forest owners, municipalities, NGOs, and researchers—in the design phase.
 - Conduct stakeholder workshops to define priorities, validate data, and co-interpret results.
 - This helps improve the legitimacy and usability of the tool and ensures indicators respond to local needs.

- [Build Local Capacity](#)
 - Offer training sessions, tutorials - how to use the ESS digital platform, and workshops to local staff and stakeholders.
 - Support the development of local expertise in using ESS platforms, interpreting results, and applying them to planning and policy processes.
 - Documentation, manuals, and case studies in the local language improve accessibility.
- [Forestry Laboratory Insight:](#)

In our pilot sites, we worked closely with local forestry actors and regional authorities to adjust the analysis scale and select indicators that were most relevant to them. This co-creation approach helped increase trust, understanding, and actual use of the results.

[Suggestion for Adapting the ESS Digital Platform for Local Contexts for Replication Sites:](#)

Following a similar participatory and flexible approach will enhance the impact of your ESS evaluations. No “one-size-fits-all” tool exists—adaptation is essential for success.

8.1.4. Conclusion for the Replication of Forestry Laboratory Example

The digitalization ESS is a powerful enabler for sustainable forest management, informed decision-making, and environmental stewardship. This methodology, inspired by Forestry Laboratory model developed in Catalonia, provides a practical and adaptable roadmap for developing similar platforms in other regions.

By following the outlined steps—ranging from data selection to visualization and long-term sustainability—stakeholders can build localized ESS platforms that support monitoring, reporting, and policy integration. While rooted in the Catalan experience, the approach is intentionally flexible to accommodate diverse environmental, technical, and governance contexts in the replication sites countries.

8.2. Guidelines for Developing a PEFC National Forest Certification System by PEFC Spain

The Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) is an international non-profit organisation that promotes the SFM of forests through certification by an independent third party. Founded in 1999, PEFC acts as a global structure that supports and recognizes national forest certification schemes developed by local stakeholders. These systems ensure that forest products are sustainably sourced, supporting both local communities and the environment.

PEFC principles are based on the protection of forest ecosystems, the preservation of biodiversity and respect for the rights of communities that depend on forest resources. This is achieved through a certification approach that is voluntary, transparent and participatory, ensuring that the standards are adaptable to the local needs and contexts of each country. The organization works closely with governments, NGOs, forest owners and industry to promote responsible management practices that balance economic, social, and environmental needs.

Currently, PEFC has certified more than 330 million hectares of forests worldwide, making it the largest and most far-reaching forest certification initiative. Its success lies in the ability to integrate global solutions with local needs, fostering acceptance of standards by various stakeholders. In addition to ensuring the sustainability of forest products, PEFC contributes to climate change mitigation and compliance with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set by the UN.

This guide aims to provide a practical framework for interested countries to develop their own national forest certification systems. The document also uses the Spanish Forest Certification System as a reference, highlighting the essential steps, the challenges overcome, and the lessons learned from its implementation. It is a useful tool for those countries seeking to implement similar systems.

8.2.1. PEFC Global Framework

Before developing a national PEFC system, it is crucial to understand the general framework and guidelines set by PEFC International. Key areas include:

- **PEFC Global Standards:** The global standards cover SFM and chain of custody, ensuring the traceability of forest products from the forest to the end consumer. The international SFM benchmark sets out the criteria and indicators we believe are vital for the sustainable management of any forest globally. However, the benchmark cannot address all the different forest types and situations found at country level, that's why this standard is designed to be flexible and adapt to the particularities of each country, ensuring that the fundamental principles of sustainability, transparency and fairness are respected globally.
- **Recognition process:** PEFC requires each national system to meet its global requirements to obtain recognition. This process includes a detailed review of national standards by PEFC International, ensuring that they are aligned with international standards and applicable at the local level. Recognition also involves monitoring to ensure ongoing compliance.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** An inclusive approach is required that integrates forest owners, local communities, industry, NGOs and government agencies. This participatory process ensures that the standards and strategies developed reflect a shared vision and are implementable at a practical level. Public consultations and multisectoral working groups are key tools in this approach.

In addition, PEFC's global framework emphasizes the importance of equity and inclusion. This means that smallholder forest owners, who account for a significant proportion of managed forests in many countries, have access to the certification scheme on fair terms. To this end, PEFC promotes tools such as group certification, which allows several smallholders to join together to share costs and benefits.

Another key component is adaptation to local contexts. Although global standards establish a common framework, each country is free to incorporate specific aspects that reflect its social, economic and environmental reality. This ensures that the system is relevant and acceptable to national actors, while maintaining consistency with international principles.

Finally, the PEFC framework includes a commitment to continuous improvement. This involves regular reviews of standards and processes, incorporating lessons learned and adapting to changes in global and local conditions, such as the impact of climate change or new market demands and regulations. Additionally, the PEFC system complements governance-focused initiatives like FLEGT and REDD+ by integrating legality frameworks, reinforcing governmental processes, and providing environmental and social safeguards. Its voluntary, flexible approach enables swift responses to stakeholder demands, ensuring the system remains effective, relevant, and supportive of SFM objectives in the long term.

8.2.2. Step-by-Step to develop a National PEFC System

1. Creation of a national structure

- a) **Identify key stakeholders:** Bring together relevant stakeholders, including forest owners, forest and tree-based industries, government representatives, and NGOs.
- b) **Establish a PEFC National Organization:** This entity will be responsible for developing and managing the certification system in the country.
- c) **Define roles and responsibilities:** It is important to assign specific tasks within the national organization, such as developing standards, coordinating public consultations, and promoting the system.
- d) **Seek institutional support:** Collaborate with government agencies, academics, and private entities to obtain political and technical support from the beginning of the process.

2. Development of a National Standard

- a) **Evaluate PEFC Global Standards:** Analyze international standards and adapt them to the local context, considering the ecological, social and economic particularities of the country.
- b) **Stakeholder mapping, public announcement & stakeholder invitation**
- c) **Establishing working group/ committee:** The working group/committee develops a draft document in which they should create specific indicators that allow evaluation of the sustainability of FM in the national context, aligned with the principles of PEFC.

- d) **Public consultation and consensus:** Conduct public consultation processes to ensure that national standards reflect local realities and have broad support. This process should include workshops, community meetings, and the receipt of written comments.
- e) **Pilot testing**
- f) **Validation of Standards:** Submit national standards to PEFC International for approval. This process may include technical reviews and adjustments based on feedback.
- g) **Formal approval & publication of the standard:** The standardising body shall approve the standard(s)/normative document(s) formally when there is evidence of consensus among the working group.

3. International recognition

Submission to PEFC International: Submit the national system for official recognition. This process includes the delivery of detailed documentation on the standardisation procedures and process, including public consultation. Additionally, as part of this process, national systems are audited by an independent third party to ensure compliance with PEFC's globally recognized sustainability benchmarks, providing transparency and credibility to the certification framework.

4. System Implementation

- a) **Training of key stakeholders:** Provide training to forest owners, auditors and other key parties to ensure they understand the requirements of the system and how to meet them.
- b) **FM Certification:** Implement independent audits to assess the sustainability of forests according to established standards. These audits must be carried out by accredited entities to ensure impartiality.
- c) **Chain of Custody Certification:** Ensures the traceability of forest products in the supply chain, from their origin in the forest to the end consumer.

- d) **Promotion of the System:** Launch communication campaigns to publicize the certification system and encourage the participation of more actors in the process.

5. Continuous improvement

- **Periodic Reviews** Adapt standards and processes based on periodic reviews. The review shall be based on consideration of feedback received during the standard's implementation and a gap analysis. This ensures that the system remains relevant and effective in the face of new challenges and changing conditions.
- **Monitoring and reporting:** Implement a monitoring system to assess the impact of the certification system and comply with PEFC International's transparency requirements. The standardising body shall establish and maintain a permanent mechanism for collecting and recording feedback on a standard.

8.2.3. Case study: The process in Spain

The development of the PEFC system Spain serves as a useful example for countries facing similar obstacles. Some key aspects of the Spanish process include:

- **Local context:** Spain adapted global standards to reflect its diversity of ecosystems and forest ownership systems. With a diverse geography that includes Mediterranean, Atlantic and mountain forests, the Spanish system had to incorporate practices adapted to each type of ecosystem, from the sustainable exploitation of cork oak to the conservation of coniferous forests in the north.
- **Broad participation:** From the beginning, a wide range of actors were integrated, ensuring representation and consensus. This included national and regional meetings with forest owners' associations, autonomous communities, and representatives of the private sector. Specific working groups were also established to address issues such as biodiversity, water management and soil conservation.
- **Achievements:** Currently, Spain has more than two million hectares of certified forests and a growing acceptance of PEFC-certified products. This success has not only built trust in international markets but has also promoted sustainable tourism and rural development in communities that depend on forest resources.

- **Challenges and solutions:** During the process, Spain faced challenges such as the fragmentation of forest ownership and the lack of technical resources in certain regions. To overcome this, group training and certification programs were implemented that allowed smallholders to access the PEFC system without incurring prohibitive costs.

The case of Spain demonstrates how a collaborative approach adapted to local conditions can result in a successful national system that contributes to both environmental sustainability and socio-economic development.

8.2.4. Challenges and solutions in developing countries

In many countries, barriers to establishing a national PEFC system include lack of government support, limited resources, and misinformation. Strategies to overcome these challenges include:

- **Awareness-raising:** Campaigns to educate the public and policymakers about the benefits of PEFC. This can include workshops, informational materials, and the use of social media to broaden the reach of information.
- **International collaboration:** Request technical and financial support from PEFC International and other organizations. Collaboration with international NGOs and multilateral agencies can provide the resources and knowledge needed to start the process.
- **Local Pilots:** Implement pilot projects in selected regions to demonstrate the value of the system. These projects can serve as case studies to convince policymakers and other key actors about the viability of the system.
- **Capacity Building:** Invest in the training of auditors and other professionals who can ensure the proper functioning of the system. This includes the development of educational programs tailored to local needs.
- **Building Multisectoral Alliances:** Work together with actors from different sectors, such as industry, local communities and universities, to generate a holistic and long-term approach that supports the sustainability of the system.

- **Adaptation to Local Conditions:** Ensure that standards and processes are relevant and applicable to the local context, considering cultural, economic, and ecological factors unique to the country.

With these strategies, countries can effectively address challenges and create forest certification schemes that benefit both the environment and the communities that depend on it.

Developing a national PEFC system is a collaborative and challenging process, but the long-term benefits to SFM and local economies are significant. With clear guidance and the support of PEFC International, countries can establish systems tailored to their specific needs, contributing to the global goal of preserving forests for future generations.

For more information and specific details about the steps described in this document, PEFC has developed the *Developing a National Forest Certification System: Your Toolkit*. This material provides a comprehensive guide detailing each stage of the national forest certification process, ensuring compliance with globally recognized sustainability standards. It is recommended as an additional resource to deepen the understanding and implementation of forest certification systems.

9. Final Remarks and Recommendations

9.1. Summary of Pros and Cons

After considering the entire process and all the specific points and steps, it is useful to extract a series of recommendations based on main pros and cons.

The main advantage of such a tool of ESS is having easily accessible databases, which is in fact the main disadvantage, the difficulties associated to acquiring and maintaining those databases. In particular, the Forestry Laboratory is as useful as was difficult to achieve.

Among the difficulties that were necessary to overcome is the selection of appropriate sources of information. Apart from the unarguable need of a national forest inventory, climate models, soil profiles or biodiversity observations are also necessary. However, those sources are not always totally reliable, due to origin (non scientific), scale (coarse), time (outdated) or space (not enough to extrapolate) reasons.

In any case, the reliability of results, depends on the use of the data. If coarse data are used to provide a general idea of available ESS at the regional level, there is no reason for concern. Similarly, very stable-in-time ESS as soil carbon at deep soil levels, could be based in old but scientifically reliable data.

Another important question to be aware is the selection of useful and representative indicators of ESS. Hereby we only provide specific examples of indicators used to obtain those ESS. For example, bird's observations of volunteers to provide a general idea of biodiversity. However, many different indicators could be used, depending on the availability of data. Following the same example of biodiversity, data could come from laborious census of species (passing through those easier to obtain in the field, as the Biodiversity Potential¹¹) to networks of nature lovers (some of them are really reliable, as those of the Butterfly Monitoring Scheme¹²).

¹¹ Gonin, P.; Larrieu, L.; Deconchat, M. 2017. Index of Biodiversity Potential (IBP)

¹² <https://butterfly-monitoring.net/>

In the end, ESS are indicators per se, as we use them as a measure of forest health. It is important to remember this, as we can use of some services versus others, depending on the information we want to provide. The most typical ESS prone to misunderstanding is blue water. The higher the quantity of trees and therefore carbon sequestration potential, the lower the quantity of blue water due to tree absorption. For this, blue water should be then considered in the balance of forest health, but cautiously when referring to a service to human populations depending on this water.

As mentioned before, the key factor is the use of these data on ESS. The information provided by PEFC Spain could be clearly used for communication purposes, demonstrating the environmental advantages of certification in a visual and intuitive manner. If considered for landscape management, could provide interesting insights about regional districts that merit special attention. At forestry scales, however, we discover that lacks enough detail to help when managing the property of a single forest owner.

This has been a first try out that demonstrated the need of more precise and updated information but also established the potential of such a powerful tool to communicate the advantages of knowing the ESS provided by our regional forests.

9.2. Communicating ESS Benefits to End Users

Following the conclusion of the previous section, the PEFC Spain ESS platform tool has proved to be successful in transferring general knowledge on ESS. Personal conversations with forest owners, technicians and researchers, and a more systematic survey distributed among a wide range of users both showed a general satisfaction about the knowledge provided and its potential applications.

Of course, the perception by different users differed since the objectives of different users are also different. Forest owners were especially perceptive to the coarse scale of the data provided, looking for a tool that could be used at the property level, while researchers missed information on how the comparison between certified and non-certified forest were made, probably thinking in the potential for further research on the subject. In any case, less

specialised users were highly enthusiastic and grateful for the potential of such an informative tool.

Confirming the previous conclusion, the tool needs more exact and reliable data in order to be used by forest owners but already shows a great potential to illustrate the benefits of sustainable forestry certification in relation to the maintenance and improvement of forest ESS.

9.3. Replication sites implementations: Example of France, Croatia and Tunisia

Guidelines for developing a certification process in other countries are developed precisely by PEFC Spain in this same document (Section 8.2.2 y 8.2.4), while a step-by-step methodology to create a similar Forestry Laboratory tool in other local contexts is described in section 8.1.3.

Basically, it is necessary to select the proper indicators of ESS depending on local environmental, technical and social contexts, engage with local stakeholders from the very beginning, and facilitate the use of the developed tool by capacity building.

Other important pieces of advice to consider are the following:

First, the platform will basically depend on the availability of data. As mentioned, the most important source of indicators to forest ESS is a reliable and updated National Forest Inventory. In any case, other sources of such valuable information could be obtained from satellite data and other GIS sources. It is also highly recommendable to dispose of climate data and models, biodiversity data coming from inventories or even citizen science campaigns, and soil profiles from bibliography or, ideally, reliable and updated inventories.

Other potential services could be considered as recreative, educational... which are also potentially easier to measure. Indicators of such services could be obtained from cadastre, national parks visits, schools, etc. On the other hand, more practical services like fire prevention or biomass production could also be of high interest and could be obtained from environmental data using appropriate models.

It should be remembered that the sources of data mentioned in this guide are related to our region, while other guides to compile appropriate indicators exist. For example, and as a result also of DigiMedFor project and the Task 3.4 implementation in the pilot 4 case, a tool to compare different existing sources of ESS will be published¹³. Another very successful example of a practical guide to obtain ESS by field observation was developed by the project LIFE CLIMARK.¹⁴

In the end, the success of the mentioned tools and their use would depend on clear objectives for each region, which must be obtained through stakeholder engagement. Combining their opinions with the available resources will surely result in the best fit tool for each context.

10. Conclusion

Based on the results obtained and presented in this guideline, it can be confirmed that PEFC-certified areas contribute to achieving higher ESS values compared to other areas that are not managed under the SFM standards of the UNE 162.002 standard. This reinforces the notion that SFM practices implemented in PEFC-certified forests in Catalonia serve as a fundamental tool for the region's sustainability.

Beyond this, the guideline has underscored the potential of digital platforms to effectively communicate complex ecological data to diverse stakeholders. While current limitations—particularly in data availability and resolution—affect its utility for property-level decision-making, the PEFC Spain ESS platform tool has proven highly effective at raising awareness, supporting regional-level planning, and illustrating the benefits of certification.

Looking ahead, success in replicating such tools in other countries will depend on adapting indicators to local contexts, engaging stakeholders early, improving data infrastructure, and ensuring capacity building. If refined and supported accordingly, the ESS platform stands as a scalable model that can bridge science, policy, and practice to advance sustainable forestry across the Mediterranean and beyond.

¹³ <https://frabjous-clafoutis-74d972.netlify.app/>

¹⁴ <https://lifeclimark.eu/>

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